

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable Documentation

NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis

Claudia M. Müller

2022-12 | Version: 1

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8344438](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344438)

nfdi4earth.de

Citation

Claudia M. Müller, Stephan Frickenhaus. 2023. *NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis (NFDI4Earth Deliverable Documentation)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344438>

License

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons “Attribution 4.0 International”](#) license.

Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through the project NFDI4Earth (DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, <https://www.nfdi.de/>).

Executive summary

This document, in its first part, aims at providing preliminary results from the evaluation of the NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue. This involves the characterisation of the different service types, and shows typical examples of services in Earth System Science. The second part of the document focuses on the identification of gaps regarding FAIRness, and missing services with the means of interviews and surveys. The envisioned target group of this documentation is mainly the NFDI4Earth service providers.

Contents

1	Introduction and Goals	1
2	NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue	1
2.1	Characterisation of Core Infrastructure and Service Types	1
2.2	Landscape of NFDI4Earth-related Infrastructures in Comparison to EOSC	5
2.3	Updated, Extended, and Current Version of the Service Catalogue	8
2.4	DCAT Catalog	9
2.5	Further Categories	9
2.6	Maximum Data Upload Size and Data Upload Type	11
3	Gap Analysis	15
3.1	Interviewing NFDI4Earth Repository Providers	15
3.2	Surveying NFDI4Earth Pilot Projects	20
3.3	Survey to identify and quantify gaps	20
3.4	Developed Questions	21
3.5	The Most Relevant Results	23
3.6	The Most Relevant Identified Gaps	26
3.7	Strategy to Address and Close the Gaps	28
	Acknowledgements	28

1 Introduction and Goals

The aim is to collect all existing and new services provided by NFDI4Earth in a Service Catalogue. This includes a detailed description of the services, such as their features, documentation, FAIRness, used standards, relation and interoperability.

A further aim is to identify critical gaps, so that the NFDI4Earth can react to it.

2 NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue

The NFDI understands a technical-organisational solution, which typically includes storage and computing services, software, processes, and workflows, as well as the necessary personnel support for different service desks as “service”¹.

2.1 Characterisation of Core Infrastructure and Service Types

In a first approach NFDI4Earth infrastructures and services, such as repositories, HPC infrastructures, Analytics Frameworks, and projects with relevance to NFDI4Earth were collected to build a comprehensive catalogue of all NFDI4Earth services and infrastructures – the NFDI4Earth “**Service Catalogue**”. The purpose is that detailed information about the services, their interactions, documentation, standards, and usage are mapped on the architecture. Their requirements are subject to individual analyses, the results of which can be found in the following chapters of this paper. The architecture description will be published in the Living Handbook, and information on the services will be published in the **Knowledge Hub**².

The first version of the “Service Catalogue” was published on the current website of the NFDI4Earth³ in 2021. In this first version 126 services and infrastructures were collected. Three different service characteristics were identified as suitable for a search and the corresponding search functions were implemented on the NFDI4Earth website. These search functions were “NFDI4Earth Relevance”, as NFDI4Earth uses several information infrastructures and data repositories, either developed and operated by members of the consortium, or relevant to Earth System Science (ESS) in general, but not operated by NFDI4Earth (see Fig. 1). Further search options were “Topics” (indexed according to DFG subject areas⁴) and the “Type of

¹ <https://base4nfdi.de/why-base4nfdi>

² NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub - Concept (NFDI4Earth Deliverable D4.3.2) <https://zenodo.org/record/7950860>

³ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2interoperate/repositories-and-infrastructures>

⁴ https://www.dfg.de/en/dfg/_profile/statutory/_bodies/review/_boards/subject/_areas/

Website” (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Figure 1: NFDI4Earth Relevance

In Fig. 1 can be found that more than 70% of the collected infrastructures and services are operated by NFDI4Earth.

In a first approach the DFG subject area was used as a search function. However, most infrastructures and services have to be sorted to more than one DFG subject area. In Fig. 2 the display of the DFG subject areas is hence only superficial and does not show the complexity of this topic.

The majority of repositories have to be allocated to more than one DFG subject area. Some examples are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Examples of repositories assigned to more than one DFG subject area

Repository	DFG subject area
GEOFON ⁵	Geology and Palaeontology; Geography; Geodesy, Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing, Geoinformatics, Cartography; Natural Sciences; Geophysics and Geodesy
GEOMAR Repository OceanRep ⁶	Natural Sciences; Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research; Geography

⁵ <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/>

⁶ <https://oceanrep.geomar.de/>

Repository	DFG subject area
Integrated Climate Data Center (ICDC) ⁷	Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research; Geography; Natural Sciences; Oceanography
International Ocean Discovery Program (IODP) ⁸	Geography; Oceanography; Geophysics and Geodesy; Geology and Palaeontology; Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Crystallography; Natural Sciences Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research
Research Data Repository of GFZ Data Services (GFZ Data Services) ⁹	Ancient Cultures; Geology and Palaeontology; Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research; Geophysics and Geodesy; Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry; Geography; Water Research; Analytical Chemistry
World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) ¹⁰	Natural Sciences; Geography; Atmospheric Science; Oceanography; Geology and Palaeontology

During the course of the project, the DFG subject area was judged to be too coarse-grained. Many research fields lack a clear distinction from other fields. As one example can be mentioned “Geochemistry”, which has to be assigned to the rather generally formulated DFG subject area “Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry”. The NFDI4Earth Task Area 3 (TA3) is currently accessing additional defined vocabularies, like the NASA¹¹, UNESCO¹² and NERC¹³ vocabularies to tackle this issue.

Another search function on the current NFDI4Earth website is “Type of Website”. Fig. 3 gives an overview of the results from the first version of the Service Catalogue. It shows the rate of collected repositories to be 4%, while apparently 68% of all service websites seem to be infrastructures.

However, the re3data project¹⁴, which provides a global research data repository registry, shows that the number of nationally hosted repositories in ESS is much higher. Therefore, the aim was to find a better distinction for the term “infrastructure”.

⁷ <https://www.cen.uni-hamburg.de/en/icdc.html>

⁸ <https://www.iodp.org/>

⁹ <https://bib.telegrafenberg.de/dataservices/>

¹⁰ <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

¹¹ <https://www.nasa.gov/offices/oct/taxonomy/index.html>

¹² <https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/>

¹³ <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>

¹⁴ <https://www.re3data.org/>

Figure 2: DFG Subject Area

Figure 3: Type of Website

2.2 Landscape of NFDI4Earth-related Infrastructures in Comparison to EOSC

Comparing the NFDI4Earth approach to the EOSC, it can be derived from the “Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives Report”¹⁵ that while the EOSC initiative aims to integrate various national and European data sources, infrastructures and services from multiple disciplines, the NFDI4Earth rather focuses its aim at infrastructures and services related to ESS. However, similar to the EOSC, the goal is to create a comprehensive and collaborative platform for researchers to access and analyse data for advancing scientific knowledge and for addressing societal challenges.

Some of the main characteristics of ESS services and infrastructures are that data is obtained from a variety of sources, such as field measurements, earth observations by satellite, or climate models, of which some examples can be found in Table 2. In general, data is documented with geospatial metadata, preferably in accordance with the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) or the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards. Usually, data and models from multiple disciplines, such as atmospheric science, oceanography, geology, geography and ecology are involved. Because of long-term observations, it is important to provide long-term storage.

Table 2: Some prevalent topics with examples

Topic	Examples of Infrastructures and Services
<p>Remote Sensing: Earth observation satellites and other remote sensing technologies play a crucial role in collecting vast amounts of data about the Earth's surface, atmosphere, and oceans. These data include measurements of temperature, precipitation, land cover, sea level, and atmospheric composition. Organisations like NASA, ESA, and national agencies, like the DLR are major contributors to the collection and dissemination of remote sensing data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESA Earth Online Data¹⁶ • Integrated Climate Data > Center (ICDC)¹⁷ • WDC-RSAT¹⁸
<p>Climate and Weather Data: Climate and weather models require extensive datasets, such as historical climate records, atmospheric observations, and oceanic measurements. Global climate data repositories, weather monitoring networks, and meteorological agencies worldwide provide access to these datasets, facilitating climate research, forecasting, and understanding long-term climate trends.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DKRZ Long-Term > Archiving¹⁹ • Climate Data Center > (CDC)²⁰ • Climate Data Store > (CDS)²¹ • Alpine Environmental Data > Analysis Center > (AlpEnDAC)²²

¹⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives – Report from the EOSC executive board working group (WG) landscape – Version 2, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/132181>

Topic	Examples of Infrastructures and Services
<p>Environmental Monitoring: Various environmental monitoring networks and sensors are deployed to track changes in air quality, water quality, soil conditions, and biodiversity. These networks contribute valuable data for environmental assessments, pollution studies, and ecosystem monitoring.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUMETSAT Climate-Monitoring > Satellite-Application > Facility (CMSAF)²³ • IOWDB²⁴ • Oceanographic Database > Search with Interactive > Navigation (ODIN 2)²⁵ • Research Data Repository of > GFZ Data Services (GFZ > Data Services)²⁶ • GEOSS Portal²⁷ • Jülich Observatory for Cloud > Evolution (JOYCE)²⁸
<p>Earth Observatories: Earth observatories, research vessels, and field stations are platforms for collecting data on specific aspects of the Earth's system. These platforms provide detailed, localised data used in conjunction with global datasets to gain comprehensive insights into the Earth's processes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earth Observation Center > (EOC) Geoservice²⁹ • IGB Freshwater Research and > Environmental Database > (FRED)³⁰ • In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System IAGOS Data Centre³¹
<p>Big Data and Machine Learning: The massive volume of Earth system data requires sophisticated data management and analysis techniques. Big data technologies and machine learning algorithms are increasingly applied to process, analyse, and extract meaningful information from these vast datasets.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oceanographic Data Center (DOD)³² • Centre for High-Performance Scientific Computing in Terrestrial Systems (HPSC TerrSys)³³ • Centre for Information Services and High-Performance Computing (ZIH)³⁴
<p>Integrative Earth System Models: To understand the complexities of the Earth's system and its interactions, scientists use integrative Earth system models. These models assimilate and integrate data from various sources to simulate and predict Earth system behaviour under different scenarios.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JASMIN Scientific Data Analysis Environment³⁵ • CMIP Data Pool (DKRZ CDP)³⁶ • Marine geoportal of hereon (coastMap)³⁷ • Ocean Science Information System (OSIS)³⁸

¹⁶ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog>

¹⁷ <https://www.cen.uni-hamburg.de/en/icdc.html>

¹⁸ https://gcos.dwd.de/DWD-GCOS/DE/nationalebeitraege/dienstleistungenfuergcos/datenzentren/wdc-rsat/wdc-rsat_node.html

¹⁹ <https://www.dkrz.de/en/services/long-term-archiving-1/long-term-archiving>

²⁰ https://www.dwd.de/EN/climate_environment/cdc/cdc_node_en.html

²¹ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>

²² <https://www.alpendac.eu/>

Just like the EOSC, whilst evolving, additional NFDI4Earth data infrastructures and services will be incorporated to further enhance the scope and impact of Earth System Science research (ESS research).

Even though the aim is to provide a knowledge platform, which can be queried in order to find research data or services, in the beginning the focus of the NFDI4Earth is the search for an appropriate repository to submit and/or find research data³⁹. re3data already consists of a comprehensive collection of repositories in ESS, and the majority of repositories are already registered here. Yet, as pointed out in a previous report⁴⁰, there is potential for enhancements regarding “API specification”, and the assignment of DOIs.

²³ https://www.cmsaf.eu/EN/Home/home/_node.html

²⁴ https://www.io-warnemuende.de/en_iowdb.html

²⁵ <https://odin2.io-warnemuende.de/>

²⁶ <https://bib.telegrafenberg.de/dataservices/>

²⁷ <https://www.geoportal.org/?m:activeLayerTileId=osm&f:dataSource=dab>

²⁸ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/de/iek/iek-8/wissenschaftliche-infrastruktur/joyce>

²⁹ <https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/>

³⁰ <https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/freshwater-research-and-environmental-database>

³¹ <https://www.iagos.org/>

³² https://www.bsh.de/EN/DATA/Climate-and-Sea/Oceanographic/_Data/_Center/oceanographic/_data/_center/_node.html

³³ <https://www.hpsc-terrsys.de/>

³⁴ https://tu-dresden.de/zih?set_language=en

³⁵ <https://jasmin.ac.uk/>

³⁶ <https://cmip-data-pool.dkrz.de/>

³⁷ https://www.hereon.de/institutes/carbon_cycles/data_coastal_research/coastmap/index.php.de

³⁸ <https://portal.geomar.de/>

³⁹ D3.2.1 First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, meta data schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth, Jonas Grieb

⁴⁰ D3.2.1 First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, meta data schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth, Jonas Grieb

2.3 Updated, Extended, and Current Version of the Service Catalogue

While re3data is harvested to build the Knowledge Hub ⁴¹, further details are independently added to the Service Catalogue in a manual way. A service or infrastructure is considered suitable and to be collected for the Service Catalogue in this way, if it is related to geography, and geoscience. The service will also be included, if the emphasis is on another research fields such as agriculture, medicine, or life science, as long as there is some relation to geography or other relevant fields of geoscience. On another level, further metadata fields were added or extended, such as:

- ROR ID
- contact details
- description
- repositoryLanguage
- apiEndpoints
- metadataStandard
- databaseAccess
- dataUploadType
- pidSystem
- geographicalExtent
- maximumUploadSize
- web-link last accessed

In alignment with the user requirements to support and improve the search function, instead of “repository” three different types were defined, which are repository, aggregator and registry. For this purpose, two major cross-domain vocabularies, Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)⁴² and schema.org⁴³ were adapted. A detailed description can be found at Grieb et al. ⁴⁴. On the basis of DCAT the terms repository, aggregator, and registry were introduced and defined. This was used for a better subdivide of the general term infrastructure.

⁴¹ D3.2.1 First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, meta data schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth, Jonas Grieb

⁴² <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#:~:text=DCAT%20enables%20a%20publisher%20to,of%20datasets%20and%20data%20services.>

⁴³ <https://schema.org/>

⁴⁴ D3.2.1 First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, meta data schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth, Jonas Grieb

In a later paragraph, it will be described, how the additional metadata field “maximum data upload size” was used to characterise the ESS services further.

2.4 DCAT Catalog

Even though DCAT offers a *Catalog* class, this class is lacking specific properties, which are required for the Knowledge Hub, with the result that three additional subclasses had to be defined. The subclasses as defined by Grieb et.al. ⁴⁵, are the following:

- **Repository:** A research data repository, which stores research data and makes it available (usually in the form of a web-based catalogue). It allows the submission of data at least from within the institution where its is run (institutional repository) and might also be available for external data submission.
- **Aggregator:** A catalogue which provides a structured metadata search. It does not host any primary data by itself, instead it harvests the metadata from remote resources and provides them in an aggregated (and optionally processed) way.
- **Registry:** A catalogue which registers metadata and thus provides (persistent) identifiers for remote resources. Examples are the Research Organization Registry (ROR), re3data, or the RDA's Metadata Standard Catalog (MSC).

2.5 Further Categories

Further categories are needed and planned. According to the collected services, possible candidates represent “web map application”, “lab instruments”, and “High-Performance Computing” (HPC). Some examples are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Examples of collected services, which could lead to the definition of further subclasses

Service	Description	Examples
Web map application:	a service, which enables the extraction, analysis, exploration and visualisation of data.	Gravity Information Services (GravIS) ⁴⁶ ; World Stress Map (WSM) ⁴⁷ WebODV ⁴⁸

⁴⁵ D3.2.1 First draft of resource information types (protocols, vocabularies, meta data schemes) in use in NFDI4Earth, Jonas Grieb

⁴⁶ <http://gravis.gfz-potsdam.de/home>

⁴⁷ <https://www.world-stress-map.org/>

⁴⁸ <https://webodv.awi.de/>

Service	Description	Examples
Lab instruments:	Measuring device or system used for conducting scientific research	International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS) ⁴⁹ ; Laboratory for nano-scale secondary ion mass spectrometry in soil, environmental and geoscience (nanoSIMS) ⁵⁰
HPC:	High-performance computing consisting of supercomputers and computer clusters to solve advanced computation problems.	Steinbuch Centre for Computing (SCC) ⁵¹ ; Centre for Information Services and High Performance Computing (ZIH) ⁵²

With the described adaptations it is possible to differentiate the term “infrastructures” in the Service Catalogue, as depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Overview of the different categories in the Service Catalogue

⁴⁹ <https://ilrs.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.lss.lis.tum.de/en/boku/service/nanoscale-secondary-ion-mass-spectrometry-nanosims/>

⁵¹ <https://www.scc.kit.edu/>

⁵² <https://tu-dresden.de/zih>

With this approach, the type of service “infrastructure” can be subdivided finer granulated into “repository”, “aggregator”, and “registry”. In contrast to the first attempt to describe services, now the different categories can be assigned better. As can be seen in Fig. 4, 52% of all collected infrastructures can now be assigned to the service type “repository”, 27% of the services can be assigned to “aggregators”, and 5% to “registries”. For the Service Catalogue mostly repositories, aggregators, and registries were collected. Other services, such as tools are collected and assessed elsewhere (see the NFDI4Earth Task Area 2 outcomes⁵³).

2.6 Maximum Data Upload Size and Data Upload Type

re3data already consists of a comprehensive collection of repositories. Yet, the question arose, in which way NFDI4Earth can create added value. The approach is to provide users with additional information depending on their needs and to facilitate the search. The aim is to identify and deliver information, which goes beyond re3data. The maximum data upload size of an infrastructure or service was one of many characteristics that was previously recorded and tested. A first approach is therefore, to use the Service Catalogue of NFDI4Earth with 150 entries, and to collect and analyse information on the maximum data upload size of repositories. The **hypothesis** was that repositories are open in respect to data upload after registration. A fixed upload size was expected, however, without any topic restrictions within the ESS field. Examples of this concept are B2Share⁵⁴ and PANGAEA⁵⁵. However, assessing the feedback from the repositories, it became quite clear that this topic is more divers. First of all, there were several repositories identified with restrictions for the data upload. These restrictions were related to **a)** a specific region in which the data was obtained, such as data from Australia, the Arctic region etc.; **b)** the topic, such as Geochemistry, or earthquakes etc.; **c)** the kind of data (model data); or **d)** the institute affiliation, such as data obtained for the IOW (Institute of Baltic Sea Research), the BGR (Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources), etc. Examples can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Repositories with restrictions in the upload

Upload Restriction	Kind of Restriction	Example Repository
a) Specific region	Data obtained in the Australian region	Australia Ocean Data Network Portal ⁵⁶
b) Topic related	Geochemistry of rocks of the oceans and continents data	GeoROC ⁵⁷
	Earthquake data	GEOFON ⁵⁸
c) Kind of data	Model data	CDS - Climate Model Data Services ⁵⁹

⁵³ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2facilitate>

⁵⁴ <https://b2share.eudat.eu/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

Upload Restriction	Kind of Restriction	Example Repository
d) Institute affiliation	BGR data	Geoportal BGR ⁶⁰
	IOW data	IOWDB ⁶¹

Quite a number of repositories do not provide an external data upload at all, however, provide their own data. As examples can be named the Climate Data Centre of the DWD⁶², the German Satellite Data Archive (DLR)⁶³, or EarthData (NASA)⁶⁴. Further services have to be distinguished from the general term “repository”, as “aggregators”, which harvest other repositories for their metadata. In general, these aggregators constitute portals such as the Earth Data Portal (Helmholtz)⁶⁵, and Geo.X (scientific institutions in Berlin)⁶⁶. Yet, there are some repositories, which are neither restricted in their topic etc., nor limited in the maximum data upload size. As example can be named the DKRZ Long-Term archiving⁶⁷ and RADAR4KIT⁶⁸.

The topic of maximum data upload size was further assessed in regard to the percentage of repositories, which allow an external data upload. A **subsample of 150** infrastructures and services was assessed, as collected in the NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue. As can be seen in Fig. 5, just **25%** of the infrastructures and services collected in the NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue constitute repositories, which allow an external data upload. Of these, **52%** provide data, but do not enable external data upload.

This raises the question to the kind of repositories, which just provide data, but do not allow a data upload. In order to be able to evaluate this further, a subsample of 79 services, which could be clearly identified as such repositories was scrutinised. Earlier portals were

⁵⁶ <https://portal.aodn.org.au/>

⁵⁷ <https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp>

⁵⁸ <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.nccs.nasa.gov/services/climate-data-services>.

⁶⁰ <https://geoportal.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/geoportal>

⁶¹ https://www.io-warnemuende.de/en_iowdb.html

⁶² https://www.dwd.de/EN/climate_environment/cdc/cdc_node_en.html

⁶³ <https://www.dlr.de/en/research-and-transfer/research-infrastructure/d-sda-user-services>

⁶⁴ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/>

⁶⁵ [https://earth-data.de/..](https://earth-data.de/)

⁶⁶ <https://www.geo-x.net/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.dkrz.de/en/services/long-term-archiving-1/long-term-archiving>

⁶⁸ <https://radar.kit.edu/radar/de/home>.

Figure 5: Data Upload for Infrastructures and Services

already mentioned in the context of aggregators and metadata harvester. Also described were repositories of data providers, which provide their own data (amongst others DLR, DWD, and NASA). As another group “Sample Collections”, such as the IODP Bremen Core Repository⁶⁹ were identified. These “Sample collections” assign persistent identifiers to samples with standardised metadata, which supports sample tracking, integration, and reuse⁷⁰, however, only physical samples are collected.

The analysis in Fig. 6 shows that 38% of these repositories can be identified as portals, which are restricted to metadata harvesting. Another 38% are repositories, which are hosted by data providers, such as NASA, DLR or DWD, and 8% depict sample collections. The remaining 16% are repositories, which provide historical data, and maps (in Fig. 6 described as “Other”).

Another question was the extent to which data upload is restricted by region, subject, or institutional affiliation, and the extent to which there are repositories that are unrestricted in their upload of ESS data, but either have no maximum upload size, or limit the maximum data upload. In short, is it possible to narrow down, the three different repository characteristics, as shown in Fig. 7, which are a) upload restricted by specific region, topic, institute affiliation, b) unrestricted upload /unlimited data upload, and c) unrestricted upload / maximum data upload size?

A **subsample of 37 repositories was** evaluated. Fig. 7 shows the result from this evaluation:

⁶⁹ <https://www.marum.de/en/Research/IODP-Bremen-Core-Repository.html>

⁷⁰ <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2021-011>.

Figure 6: Repositories with no external upload

Figure 7: Repositories differentiated by their upload characteristic “restricted” and “unrestricted”

70% of the repositories in one or other way are **restricted** in their upload of data (specific region, topic, institute affiliation). However, 10% of the evaluated repositories allow an **unrestricted** upload of data, but with a maximum data upload size, while 20% allow an unrestricted upload without a distinct upper limit in the data upload.

It can be summarised that information on the data upload size can be used to characterise or even classify services. During the evaluation it had to be discovered, that even though the maximum data upload size is an important information for the user, this information cannot be extracted easily from the according web pages. It takes more than “just” screening the web page for information, and it should be considered that a way is found to make this important information more easily accessible. Yet, the metadata about the upload size could be collected in a structured way via a registry such as re3data. Therefore, the cooperation with registries like re3data is of great significance.

3 Gap Analysis

One of the aims of NFDI4Earth is to identify missing interfaces of ESS user workflows, detecting needs for services and performance improvements, enhancing convergence with common standards, and detecting demands for new services. In a joined effort, the data repository providers, and NFDI4Earth pilots of the 1st Cohort of Pilots 2022-2023⁷¹ were asked for their opinion.

3.1 Interviewing NFDI4Earth Repository Providers

In order to be able to interview repository providers, a questionnaire was formulated with questions covering the relevant ESS standards (such as OGC, and ISO19115), interfaces (such as Application-Programming-Interface (APIs)), form of access (open or restricted), and the software products with which the repository are build. The questionnaire was sent out to 12 NFDI4Earth affiliated repository providers (Table 5).

Table 5: List of repository providers to whom the questionnaire was sent

Repository	Institution
PANGAEA ⁷²	MARUM / AWI
ICDC ⁷³	CEN / University Hamburg
Marine Data Portal ⁷⁴	AWI / DAM
EOC Geoservice ⁷⁵	DLR

⁷¹ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/pilots>

Repository	Institution
OceanRep ⁷⁶	GEOMAR
WDC-Climate ⁷⁷	DKRZ
Edaphobase ⁷⁸	Senckenberg
Research Data Repository ⁷⁹	GFZ Data Services
Ocean Science Information System (OSIS) ⁸⁰	GEOMAR
GEOFON ⁸¹	GFZ
Tereno ⁸²	UFZ
Alpine Environmental Data Analysis Center (AlpEnDAC) ⁸³	LRZ
Data Exchange Portal ⁸⁴	MPI for Biogeochemistry

Since the last two repositories, as listed in Table 5, are projects with an uncertain funding future, the repository providers were interviewed only for a general knowledge exchange. In the following chapter each question and a summary of the answers are listed.

Answers Concerning Metadata Standards

The question "Which common (metadata) standards are implemented in your infrastructure (repositories and services⁸⁵), like ISO 19115⁸⁶, DataCite⁸⁷?" was answered as can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Used metadata standards

⁷² <https://www.pangaea.de/>

⁷³ <https://www.cen.uni-hamburg.de/en/icdc.html>

⁷⁴ <https://marine-data.de/>

⁷⁵ <https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/>

⁷⁶ <https://oceanrep.geomar.de/>

⁷⁷ <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

⁷⁸ <https://portal.edaphobase.org/>

⁷⁹ <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/index.html>

⁸⁰ https://portal.geomar.de/de/kdmi#_48_INSTANCE_5P8d_=metadata%2F%3F

⁸¹ <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/>

⁸² <https://www.tereno.net/>

⁸³ <https://www.vao.bayern.de/index.htm>

⁸⁴ <https://www.bgc-jena.mpg.de/geodb/projects/Home.php>

⁸⁵ <https://www.forschungsdaten.info/themen/veroeffentlichen-und-archivieren/repositorien/> and <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Repository> (both not available in English)

⁸⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

⁸⁷ <https://datacite.org/>

Standard	Number of repositories
ISO19115	2
ISO19115/ISO19135	1
ISO19115/19139	1
ISO 19115/19119/19139	1
ISO19139	1
ISO with the INSPIRE Profile	3
INSPIRE >	1
OGC and OGC CSW 2.02	3
DataCite	3
Dublin Core	2
Community standards station xml	1
SAMD archive conforms to the SAMD standard ⁸⁸	1
NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) ⁸⁹	1

Most repositories follow more than one standard, like ISO 19115/19119/19139, OGC CSW 2.02, and INSPIRE, or follow the ISO standard in different combinations.

Despite the fact that INSPIRE is based widely on ISO 19115 (datasets) and ISO 19119 (services), conformance of an ISO 19115 metadata set to the ISO 19115 core seems not to guarantee the conformance to INSPIRE. Likewise, full conformance to ISO 19115 requires provision of additional metadata elements not necessarily compliant to INSPIRE.

Darwin Core biodiversity data was not included, as it contains in particular occurrence and taxonomic data derived from observations of organisms, biological specimens, samples etc. Darwin Core does not describe geo-objects, in contrast to the also common ABCD (Access to Biological Collection Data). GeoCASE, which aims to be an ESS counterpart of GBIF (major biodiversity data aggregator) uses the ABCD Extension for Geosciences (ABCD-EFG, cp. <https://geocase.eu/about>).

Answers Concerning Data Curation

The question “If standards are implemented, is the (meta) data curated accordingly and resulting data quality information published?” was answered by 81% of the providers. 72% of the repository providers stated that the metadata is curated. One provider explained that no manual curation of individual harvested content takes place, which was rated as “no curation”.

⁸⁸ <http://doi.org/10.17616/R3D944>

⁸⁹ <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

Answers Concerning Available APIs

The question “Is there one or more application programming interfaces (APIs)? If yes, please answer the following questions (if possible)!

- Which protocols are used?
- What is the URL of the API?
- What is the URL of the documentation?”

was answered as can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Application programming interfaces used

Interface	Number
OAI-PMH	4
REST-API	3
OGC CSW	2
JSON-LD	2
FDSN define the protocols and APIs http://www.fdsn.org/services/	1
THREDDS server, accessible via OPeNDAP (no API provided)	1

This can be interpreted to the effect that about 50% of the questioned providers are using OAI-PMH. However, the REST API, CSW API, and JSON-LD API are used as well, and in many cases in combination with at least one of these options, which are OAI-PMH with OGC CSW; or OAI-PMH with JSON-LD API and REST API. One provider stated that the THREDDS server OPeNDAP is used, a web server that provides metadata and data access for scientific datasets.

Answers Concerning Open Access

The answer to the question “Is there open or restricted access or how is your infrastructure technically accessible to NFDI4Earth (Conditions for Access and Use, Limitations on Public Access)?” is in summary that metadata generally is accessible without restriction, but access to the research data is governed by various aspects, such as moratorium periods and individual licenses.

Answers Concerning Implemented Data Management Software

Answering the question “Which open-source products, or technically available product is the infrastructure built with, e.g. R, CKAN?” the following products were named:

- Oracle database
- Elasticsearch (<https://www.elastic.co/de/elasticsearch/>)
- DataCite Metadata Store
- pangaeaR
- Thredd Server
- Live Access Server
- Geo Server
- EPrints
- SeisComP (<https://www.seiscomp.de/>)
- GeoNetwork
- PostgreSQL with PostGIS
- OpenAPI
- Symfony
- Java
- PHP
- iptables
- wireguard
- MapServer
- BioCase

The answers show the diversity of the used data management software in the ESS community.

Answers Concerning Certification

The question “Which certificates does the infrastructure use, e.g. CoreTrustSeal⁹⁰, nestor (Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives)⁹¹?” was answered as can be seen in the Table 8.

Table 8: Certificates

⁹⁰ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁹¹ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/siegel.html?nn=182416

Certification	Number
certified according to ISO 9001	1
CoreTrustSeal	4
Not certified	6

From the answers it can be quite clearly derived that about 50% of the data providers are not certified. The majority (about 40%) of the certified infrastructures apply the CoreTrustSeal.

Answers Concerning Update Intervals

The question “Are regular updates performed (in respect to metadata schemata or source code) and if so, in which cycles do they take place?” can be answered in summary that about 70% of the questioned providers have not specified the update intervals. Further answers were weekly, on best effort basis and every 4 years.

3.2 Surveying NFDI4Earth Pilot Projects

As another group the pilot projects and incubator labs were identified as potential partners to be interviewed for the identification of gaps in ESS RDM (Earth System Science Research Data Management). As outlined in the proposal, the aim is that results from the gap analyses are triggering further action, such as the implementation of missing services on a prototype basis. The “First Cohort of Pilots 2022-2023”⁹² consisted of 14 projects, of which 12 projects were finished or about to be finished in March 2023. Therefore these 12 pilot projects were contacted.

3.3 Survey to identify and quantify gaps

Questions were developed regarding interdisciplinary cooperation, interoperability issues, used Infrastructure and (software) tools. In order to be able to quantify the results better, the decision was taken to use an online survey tool. Involved with a similar task, the questions for the survey were developed together with the NFDI4Earth User Support Network⁹³. The purpose was to avoid doubling of interviews and surveys, which might basically have a very similar purpose, but a different emphasis, or target group. The aim is also to use the questions again at a later stage and possibly for different target groups. In the end, feedback was received from 9 pilot projects. The survey was launched on March 2, 2023 and ended in April 30, 2023.

⁹² <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/pilots>

⁹³ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2facilitate/user-support-network>

3.4 Developed Questions

Section A: General Question Group

A1. What is your role in/contribution to NFDI4Earth?

Options: Pilot project, Incubator Lab, Participant, CoApps, Interest Group, Other

A2. What is your domain of discipline?

Data management, Software Developer, Research Scientist in Earth System Science, Other

Section B: Question Group Regarding Tools

B1. Which were the main tools, like software that were used in your project.

Please name them in the field below.

B2. Regarding the listed tools you have used throughout your project, please rate how well they fulfilled the following criteria?

Does apply very well, does apply in most cases, does not apply at all (Openly accessible, Self-explanatory, Well documented)

B3. How would you describe your experience with software tools and computational infrastructure you used in your projects? Did you encounter any of these obstacles?

Limitations in handling the data, Storage-size limitations, Interoperability issues, Challenges working collaboratively, Missing guidance and documentation, Other

Section C: Question Group regarding Infrastructures

C1. Which were the main infrastructures (portals, research repositories, and archives) that were used in your project.

a) Please name them in the field below.

b) Does apply very well, does apply in most cases, does not apply at all (Openly accessible, Self-explanatory, Well documented)

C2. You have just listed the main infrastructures (portals, archives, and research data repositories) you have used throughout your project in the previous question. Do the following options "openly accessible", "self-explanatory", and "well documented" apply, and to which degree?

Does apply very well, does apply in most cases, does not apply at all (Openly accessible, Self-explanatory, Well documented)

C3. On a portal website like Geoportal (GDI-DE) or GEOSS Portal, what are the main services you would expect to find?

Analytical tools /software to process your data, Visualisation tools, Viewer, Computational resources, Other

C4. On the website of a research data repository such as e.g. PANGAEA or GEOFON, what are the main services you would expect to find?

API for easy access to the infrastructure, Analytical tools / software to process your data, Visualisation tools, Viewer, Computational resources, Other

C5. On the website of an archive such as e.g., the German Satellite Data Archive or World Data Center for Climate (WDCC), what are the main services you would expect to find?

API for easy access to the archive, Analytical tools / software to process your data, Visualisation tools, Viewer, Computational resources, Other

Other

C6. In the NFDI4Earth we are developing a single point of access with the working title "OneStop4All". If you are not familiar with the idea, you can find more information on the NFDI4Earth website at <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2facilitate/onestop4all>.

What kind of information do you expect on a main portal website, as we want to create it as a OneStop4All?

Research data up- and download Information on fitting repositories and data archives, Training material, Search for experts on a specific research field, Topic related information (e.g. data management, data management plan, best practice), Software tools, Other

Section D: Open Questions

D1. Have you used a portal to search for data or tools before? If so, were there some features you particularly liked or disliked?

D2. In your opinion should a research data portal offer in-person support

(e.g. a help desk)? If yes, which part of your work would benefit from in-person support?

If no, please skip to next question.

D3. Embedding of your ESS domain in the NFDI4Earth: Do you feel that your ESS domain is well represented in the NFDI4Earth environment? If not, please make suggestions how this can be improved.

D4. Do you have experience in working with data management plans? If yes, where do you see room for improvement?

If not, please skip to next question.

D5. Did you encounter any constraints regarding interdisciplinary cooperation? If so, please describe.

Section E: Question Group Datasets

E1. You have certainly used data in your project. Please specify the size and format (raster, vector) of the data you used.

E2. In case you produce a dataset in your project, have you annotated your data with metadata? If yes, please specify, which metadata standard you have used.

E3. If you produced a dataset in your project, have you considered long term archiving?

Yes, No

Section F: One last question...

F1. We would like to follow-up on interesting gaps and topics. If you were available for a follow-up interview, please let us know your email address in the field below, and / or a comment.

Email address

Thank you for your support. Yours NFDI4Earth (TA2 and TA3)

3.5 The Most Relevant Results

The following software tools were used in the pilot project, as can be seen in Table 9. As categories “General Software and Tools” and according to the main disciplines of the pilot projects “Tools for Geography”, Tools for Marine Data, and “Climate and Meteorology Data Tools” were determined. Most of the interview partners basically use the same “General Software and Tools” like GitHub, R, Python, or Julia. But the different disciplines within the ESS field mention quite different software tools. As an example, can be mentioned that SeaDataNet is explicitly used for marine data, while CDO an CMOR are used in Meteorology.

Table 9: Software tools used in the pilot projects

Category	Software Tools
General Software and Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GitHub • ML diagnostic packages • Streamlit • PostgreSQL • Julia / YAXArrays.jl • VSCode, R, Python, AWK*
	*programming environment

Category	Software Tools
Tools for Geography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Cubes • ESMValTool • GDAL/OGR • GRASS GIS
Tools for Marine Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SpatioTemporal Asset > Catalogs (STAC) • ecoSound-web • Mikado (SeaDataNet-metadata > generator) • geo-seas (SeaDataNet) • MDM (MassenDatenManagement)
Climate and Meteorology Data Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D-Ship • climate data operators (CDO) • climate model output rewriter (CMOR)

Table 10 lists the repositories as mentioned by the pilot projects according to their scientific domain. These are mainly data repositories related to “Geospatial and Geographical Data”, “Marine Data”, “Geochemistry Data”, “Climate and Meteorology Data”, and with Metbase even “Extraterrestrial Data”. The different categories show again the diversity in ESS data. However, it is noticeable that the number of repositories provided for Marine Data is especially high, while for Geospatial and Geographical Data repositories were used, which are not necessarily part of the science community, such as the Google Earth Engine. In general, the repositories used are not limited to the national level, but are quite international in scope.

Table 10: Repositories according to discipline used by the pilots

Discipline	Repository
Geospatial and Geographical Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BGR Geoportal⁹⁴ • ESGF⁹⁵ • Sentinel Hub⁹⁶ • INSPIRE⁹⁷ • Earth System Data Cube⁹⁸ • CODE-DE⁹⁹ • EOC Geoservice¹⁰⁰ • Google Earth Engine • SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs Specification¹⁰¹

Discipline	Repository
Marine Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • marine-data.de¹⁰² • Seismic Data Network Access Point¹⁰³ • SeaDataNet¹⁰⁴ • GEO-Seas¹⁰⁵ • Seismic Data Library System¹⁰⁶ • PANGAEA¹⁰⁷ • NOAA¹⁰⁸ • GEOMAR In-house archives¹⁰⁹ • Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)¹¹⁰
Geochemistry Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial portals for seismic data • GEOROC¹¹¹
Climate and Meteorology Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AusGeochem¹¹² • WDC Climate¹¹³
Extraterrestrial Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESA Climate Office¹¹⁴ • Metbase¹¹⁵ • Astromaterials Data System¹¹⁶

⁹⁴ <https://geoportal.bgr.de/mapapps/resources/apps/geoportal/index.html?lang=de/#/>

⁹⁵ <https://esgf.llnl.gov/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

⁹⁷ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

⁹⁸ <https://deepcube-h2020.eu/technology/earth-system-data-cube/>

⁹⁹ <https://code-de.org/de/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/>

¹⁰¹ <https://stacspec.org/en>

¹⁰² <https://marine-data.de/?site=providers>

¹⁰³ <https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.seadatanet.org/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.geo-seas.eu/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.ogs.it/it/progetti/seismic-data-library-s>

The question “How would you describe your experience with the software tools and computing infrastructure you have used in your projects? Have you encountered any of the following obstacles?” was intended to identify gaps in this field. Fig. 8 shows that interoperability issues, and limitations in handling the data were the main obstacles.

In another question the pilot projects were asked, which the main services were, they expected to find. As the main expected service an API for easy access can be identified. Yet, the pilot projects identified “Viewer” as the second most important service. The results can be viewed in Fig. 9.

3.6 The Most Relevant Identified Gaps

As the most relevant gaps “interoperability issues”, “missing services”, “limitation in handling the data”, “sustainability”, and “issues with interdisciplinary cooperation” can be listed.

Regarding lack in **interoperability**, for some ESS fields metadata standards are still missing. In this analysis the fields passive acoustic monitoring, isotopes, and seismic data were identified as effected research fields.

Regarding missing **services**, 80% of the pilot projects stated that they had no experience with data management plans. Further, missing repositories were identified. For complex data, such as seismic data there are no suitable repositories to store this kind of data, and up to now it was mostly stored on private computers, or portable storage. Passive acoustic monitoring software tools were named as not well embedded.

Further, **limitations in handling the data** were identified as a gap. Some services still lack

ystem-sdls

¹⁰⁷<https://www.pangaea.de/>

¹⁰⁸<https://www.noaa.gov/>

¹⁰⁹<https://oceanrep.geomar.de/>

¹¹⁰<https://www.marine-geo.org/index.php>

¹¹¹<https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp>

¹¹²<https://ausgeochem.auscope.org.au/#/>

¹¹³<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

¹¹⁴<https://climate.esa.int/en/esa-climate/esa-climate-office/>

¹¹⁵<https://metbase.org/>

¹¹⁶<https://www.astromat.org/>

Figure 8: Obstacles when using software tools and / or computational infrastructure

Figure 9: Main Expected Services

download speed, with long waiting times to access the data products. Not properly working visual interface, when selecting a specific area, were listed.

In regard of **sustainability**, as already mentioned earlier, some services were developed as projects. However, as soon as the funding is terminated, the service ends. Funding schemes should make sure before the start of the project that the provider will keep the project running. This should be a prerequisite of granting the funding.

In respect to **Interdisciplinary cooperation** the pilot project rated a lack of time/interest from other disciplines. An obstacle is that different standards are used in particular to interface tools and / or software. The challenge is that different groups and communities sometimes bet on different programming languages and packages to work with data (e.g. Python vs Julia, choice of library).

3.7 Strategy to Address and Close the Gaps

The aim of the NFDI4Earth is to close the identified gaps. However, with the NFDI4Earth core components, many of the above-mentioned points are already addressed. In addition, there is much to be done to actively support the community, for example, to further develop standards according to community needs. Workflows for complex or topic related data need to be developed collaboratively, as does the use of services such as data management plans.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Christin Henzen, Jonas Grieb, Claus Weiland, Christopher Purr, Johannes Munke, Alexander Wellmann, and Stephan Hachinger for their support, advices and contributions.